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Automatic Landslide Detection Using Google Earth Engine, a case study for Quang Nam Province, Vietnam

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Abstract— Accurate and timely detection of new landslides is critical for updating landslide susceptibility assessment and developing effective mitigation and response strategies. In this study, an automated procedure for detecting landslides is developed using Sentinel-2 images and Google Earth Engine. Based on a known event date, the best pair of pre- and post-event satellite images is first selected to make a change detection analysis based on the difference of normalised difference vegetation index (dNDVI). Geomorphological filters are then used to select potential landslides from pixels affected by large vegetation changes. This automatic-landslide inventory is compared with a benchmark landslide inventory manually drawn on high-resolution images to assess whether the technique is sufficiently robust. We calibrated this approach in Phuoc Thanh commune, Phuoc Son district, Quang Nam province, which was severely affected by a storm in October 2020. The method is then applied to all mountainous districts of the Quang Nam Province for each rainy season between 2020 and 2024 to produce a multi-temporal landslide inventory in this highly forested region. The Google Earth Engine scripts allow this procedure to be quickly repeated in new areas and create an inventory map for large areas. However, other ground surface changes due to deforestation, wildfires, accelerated erosion, construction, and logging can also cause a decrease in vegetation cover, which can lead to false positives.

I. INTRODUCTION

On the morning of October 28th 2020, heavy downpours and strong winds triggered by storm struck the mountainous regions of central Vietnam, leading to the occurrence of thousands of landslides and flashfloods in Quang Nam province. These events

led to tens of fatalities, and the destruction of multiple houses and roads [1].

Landslide detection with reliable information regarding landslide location and timing is critical for assessing landslide susceptibility and developing effective mitigation and prevention strategies. In the past, this task remained challenging due to the lack of remote sensing and geographic information systems. Therefore, traditional methods for detecting landslides involved intensive fieldwork and manual image interpretation of aerial photographs [2]. These approaches demand expert knowledge, specialized training, and adherence to a standardized detection protocol. Besides, these conventional techniques entail significant labor and are time-consuming.

Nowadays, remote sensing data plays a vital role in landslide detection and mapping due to the provision of critical information on land cover that facilitates the identification of a landslide affected areas [3]. New methodologies have been proposed in recent years to semi-automatically or automatically map landslides with the use of earth observation data.

This study focuses on calibrating an algorithm for automatic detection and mapping of landslides caused by the storm in October 2020, in Phuoc Thanh commune, Quang Nam, Vietnam, through free optical satellite data in Google Earth Engine (GEE). The developed approach is then applied to all mountainous districts of the Quang Nam Province for each rainy season between 2020 and 2024 to produce a multi-annual landslide inventory in this highly forested region.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study area

Quang Nam province is located in the center of Vietnam [4] and is extent over 10,574 km² (Figure 1). The population of the province was 1,945,000 people in 2022, representing a population density of 183 inhab/km², with most people living in the coastal districts [4]. Quang Nam province has a relatively complex topography that progressively descends from the West to the East. There are six mountainous districts in the West, including Dong Giang, Tay Giang, Nam Giang, Nam Tra My, Bac Tra My, and Phuoc Son districts.

Figure 1. Map showing the study area, Quang Nam province in Vietnam (source: Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Digital Elevation Model with a 30m spatial resolution)

The test area is Phuoc Thanh commune, with an area of 62 km², a mountainous commune located in Phuoc Son district (Fig. 1). The population of the commune was 1,891 people in 2019 [4], representing a population density of 30 inhab/km² [6]. The population in the area is quite sparse, principally composed of ethnic minorities depending on farming, with a poor livelihood.

This area experiences a tropical climate with the highest rainfall levels in Vietnam [7]. It has one rainy season and one dry season, with an average annual temperature of about 25.6°C [6]. The rainy season begins in August-September, reaching a peak in October and November before ending in November - December, with mean annual rainfall ranging from 2000 to 2500 mm/year [8].

B. Data

In this study, an automated procedure for the detection of landslides is developed using Sentinel-2 with 10 m visible and near-infrared bands. Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM)

Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a 30-meter spatial resolution (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>) is used to describe the topography (Table I). Moreover, high-resolution images from Google Earth will be used to conduct a manual inventory of landslides. The pre- and post-event images available for analysis are from March 6, 2019, and October 1, 2021, respectively ((Table II).

TABLE I. SENTINEL-2 IMAGES USED IN THIS STUDY

Variable	Remarks	Value
Image source	Sentinel-2	Band RGB; NIR 10 m spatial resolution
Topographic map	SRTM DEM	30 m resolution
Event date	Date of the storm-trigger landslide occurred in the study area	October 28 th , 2020
Pre-event image	Use for automatic detection	January 23 rd , 2020
Post-event image	Use for automatic detection	February 16 th , 2021

TABLE II. HIGH-RESOLUTION IMAGES USED FOR MANUAL LANDSLIDE MAPPING IN THIS STUDY

Variable	Remarks	Value
Image source	Google Earth	0.3 m spatial resolution
Pre-event image	Use for manual inventory mapping	March 6 th , 2019
Post-event image	Use for manual inventory mapping	October 1 st , 2021

C. Methods

Our landslide detection approach aims to detect landslides based on change in vegetation cover (measured by NDVI) and geomorphological filters (Fig. 2). An image pair is selected based on the known date of the event during the rainy season. The selection criteria for the pre-event and post-event image prioritize images with the least cloud cover available, acquired during the same time of year to minimize the effects of canopy cover changes across seasons [9].

To improve the identification of the best pair of images, we manually draw sample of landslides and non-landslides areas on the GEE interface, to extract NDVI time series from Sentinel-2 data from 2019 to the present and process with GEE. This step aims to assess the changes in vegetation cover in the time series of images and identify the landslide occurrence. This process aids in establishing the likely date range for a landslide occurrence and provides an initial assessment of the event's timing.

In the second step, one cloud-free scene is selected in the dry season preceding the event and one following it, to compute the dNDVI by subtracting the pre-event from the post-event NDVI image. The dNDVI threshold was defined based on the comparison of the NDVI time series of the affected and not affected areas by landslide, and a comparing the dNDVI statistical distribution for landslide and non-landslides areas. Moreover, a digital elevation model (DEM) is used for filtering results of the

landslide detection based on dNDVI, as the slope is one of the contributing factors in landslide mapping [10, 11]. A manual inventory of landslides conducted on Google Earth for the study area is used to calibrate our automatic algorithm and geomorphological filters. Part of the manual landslide inventory also serves as validation data for the automated detection methods.

Figure 2. Schematic overview of the landslide detection algorithm

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed methodology was calibrated to the automatic detection of landslides in Phuoc Thanh commune, Phuoc Son district, Quang Nam province, based on dNDVI of pre-event (23 January 2020) and post-event (16 February 2021) Sentinel-2 images. Figure 3 shows the NDVI time series of the area affected and the unaffected area by landslides.

Figure 3. The NDVI time series of the area affected by landslides compared with the time series averaged over a region not affected by landslides.

In areas unaffected by landslides, the NDVI time series exhibit a relatively stable seasonal pattern from 2019 to the present,

fluctuating between 0.6 and 0.85. In contrast, regions impacted by landslides experienced a significant drop in NDVI, decreasing from 0.85 to 0.35 after the event. Over the subsequent years, NDVI gradually recovered, reaching 0.7 by 2023.

Figure 4. The distribution of dNDVI of the area affected by landslides (blue) compared with the dNDVI of the areas unaffected by landslides (red).

To define the dNDVI threshold for landslide detection, the training dataset was used for parameter calibration. A threshold value can be selected where the separation between the two classes (landslide and non-landslide) is most evident by analyzing their distributions using boxplots and histograms, as in Figure 4. A dNDVI threshold of -0.1 is identified as delivering the best detection accuracy when applied for validation. Moreover, a slope threshold of 10° is selected, to differentiate landslide affected areas (on steep slopes) from zones affected by material deposition (lower slopes).

Figure 5. (a) Sentinel-2 pre-event image acquired on 23 January 2020, (b) Sentinel-2 post-event image acquired on 16 February 2021, (c) dNDVI map, (d) comparison between automatic landslide and manual landslide inventory

From the pre- and post-event images (Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b), we obtained the dNDVI (Fig. 4c) that was applied for landslide detection. Finally, the automatic landslide inventory was compared visually with the manual mapping (Fig. 4d) based on high-resolution images. Visual comparison highlight good performance of the automatic mapping, except for some locations where images are affected by cloud or cloud shadows. Mapping of the full extent and complex shapes of landslides affected areas remains more challenging. A quantitative accuracy assessment needs to be carried out after applying the algorithm to all districts affected by landslides.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work developed a method for rapidly detecting landslides with promising performance. The process is automatic, resulting in a landslide inventory map. This approach does not require expensive, high-resolution data. Additionally, the Google Earth Engine scripts are simple, allowing the procedure to be quickly replicated in new areas and enabling the creation of inventory maps for large regions. The method will be applied to all mountainous districts of Quang Nam Province for each rainy season between 2020 and 2024 to generate a multi-annual landslide inventory in this highly forested region. However, it is also noted that other ground surface changes, for instance, due to deforestation, wildfires, accelerated erosion, construction, and logging, can also cause a decrease in vegetation cover, which can lead to false positives.

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